

**What Tree for Each Place
in Agroforestry for Conifers**

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Silvopastoral systems established under *Pinus silvestris* L. in Galicia (NW Spain).

Conifers are usually spread across Europe as pioneer forest species able to initially colonize degraded soils. The most widespread of conifer species in Europe is *Pinus silvestris* usually associated with high altitudes in the South of Europe but can be found at sea level in the north of Europe. Conifers growing rate and structure determines the compatibility with agroforestry practices as this determines the amount of light that can reach the understory. When young conifers develop a conic tree shape reduces in a very important way the productivity under their canopy. Therefore, there is a direct relationship between the amount of production of the understory and the canopy cover. Pasture production is reduced by 50% when canopy cover reaches the 50%. From this moment pasture is drastically reduced until the full canopy cover happens. From this moment onwards, the light does not reach the needles below and they start to fall down causing a complete reduction on pasture production due to the growing accumulation of leaf litter on it. This leaf litter accumulation happens until the canopy occupies around 1-2 meters of the top height of the tree. Afterwards, light starts to reach the understory favoring the incorporation of the litter into the soil and producing and increasing biomass production of the understory. This phenomenon is quite common in *Pinus species*, being the amount of time on which the understory is unable to grow dependent on the growth rate, *Pinus sylvestris* has usually a harvesting time between 80-120 years, being similar in *Pinus pinaster* subspecies *Mediterranea* and much lower in the subspecies *Atlantica*. Other conifers are more compatible with the understory as it is the case of *Cupressus sempervivens* or even less compatible as happens with the *Pseudotsuga menziesii*.

María Rosa Moquera-Losada, José Javier Santiago-Freijanes, Nuria Ferreiro-Domínguez, Ana Couso-Viana, Antonio Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Rosa Romero-Franco, Juan Luis Fernández-Lorenzo, María Pilar González-Hernández, Francisco Javier Rodríguez-Rigueiro

University of Santiago de Compostela (USC)

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